

Multi-Disciplinary Analysis of Nuclear Fuel Geometries Incorporating the Schwarz-H Surface

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ABSTRACT

Triply Periodic Minimal Surfaces (TPMS) exhibit excellent heat transfer and mechanical properties, making them an attractive geometry for innovative nuclear fuels. This paper focuses on the impact of the orientation of a specific TPMS lattice: the Diamond lattice. By applying a specific rotation to this lattice, another notable TPMS, the Schwarz-H lattice, is obtained. The study involves a comprehensive analysis of the lattices' properties, including mechanical comparisons using MOOSE, neutron physics comparisons using OpenMC, and CFD analysis using STAR-CCM+. Results indicate that the Schwarz-H lattice exhibits better stress distribution under compression. The orientation of the lattice has no effect on its neutron physics properties. Preliminary CFD results suggest that the thermal properties depend on the lattice orientation. While the study highlights the importance of lattice orientation on thermal behavior, definitive conclusions require further validation and uncertainty quantification. The findings justify continued research to optimize TPMS lattice orientations for nuclear fuel applications.

Keywords: TPMS, OpenMC, STAR-CCM+, MOOSE

1. INTRODUCTION

Innovation in nuclear fuels is essential for the advancement of both current and future nuclear reactor designs. Recent years have seen numerous proposals for innovative fuel solutions, including accident tolerant fuel [1], new cladding materials [2], and high-assay low enriched uranium (HALEU) [3, 4]. Advancements in additive manufacturing have opened up new opportunities for innovation by enabling alterations to the geometry of nuclear fuel. Triply Periodic Minimal Surfaces (TPMS) have been explored as potential shapes for heat exchangers [5, 6] and as alternatives to traditional cylindrical fuel rods in nuclear applications [7, 8].

TPMS structures exhibit excellent heat transfer and mechanical properties [8]. However, the significant pressure drop caused by coolant flow through the lattice remains a major drawback [8]. While there are methods to mitigate this issue, they often come at the expense of fuel density or cooling efficiency.

Among the various TPMS configurations, the *Diamond* TPMS, also known as *Schwarz-D* in the literature, appears to be the most promising candidate for fuel design [7, 8]. Despite its potential, there has been limited optimization of this lattice to reduce pressure drop.

Mathematical analysis reveals interesting symmetry properties of the *Diamond* TPMS. By rotating the lattice to align all planes of symmetry vertically, it is hypothesized that the mechanical and cooling properties of the lattice can be enhanced without affecting its neutron physics characteristics.

This article aims to verify this hypothesis. Section 2 introduces the *Diamond* TPMS and its rotated version, along with their properties. Section 3 presents neutron physics calculations for both infinite lattices. Section 4 details the results of solid mechanical analysis on these lattices. Section 5 discusses the flow analysis results obtained with STAR-CCM+.

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2. MATHEMATICAL DEVELOPMENT

The implicit equation of the *Diamond* TPMS is given by:

$$\sin(x) \sin(y) \sin(z) + \sin(x) \cos(y) \cos(z) + \cos(x) \sin(y) \cos(z) + \cos(x) \cos(y) \sin(z) = c, \quad (1)$$

where c is a constant (also referred to as the *isovalue*) and (x, y, z) are the coordinates of a point in space. This equation can be rewritten in a compact form as:

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(\sin(x + y + z) + \sin(-x + y + z) + \sin(x - y + z) + \sin(x + y - z) \right) = c. \quad (2)$$

Two successive rotations are performed on points in space:

- A rotation of -45° around the Y-axis,
- A rotation of $\arcsin(1/\sqrt{3}) \approx +35.2644^\circ$ around the X-axis.

These rotations transform the point $(1, 1, 1)$ to $(0, 0, \sqrt{3})$. In other words, the cubic lattice is rotated onto its tip. The resulting rotation matrix is:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \\ -\frac{1}{\sqrt{6}} & \frac{2}{\sqrt{6}} & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{6}} \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3)$$

The TPMS equation becomes:

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(\sin(\sqrt{3} \cdot z) + \sin \left(-\sqrt{2} \cdot x + \frac{2}{\sqrt{6}} \cdot y + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \cdot z \right) + \sin \left(-\frac{4}{\sqrt{6}} \cdot y + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \cdot z \right) + \sin \left(\sqrt{2} \cdot x + \frac{2}{\sqrt{6}} \cdot y + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \cdot z \right) \right) = c. \quad (4)$$

This equation has the following properties:

- Invariance under 120° and 240° rotations around the Z-axis.
- Invariance under the *OYZ* symmetry plane, and consequently under this plane rotated by 120° and 240° around the Z-axis.
- Invariance under translation by $(0, 0, n \cdot \pi\sqrt{6})$, and under translation by this vector rotated by multiples of 60° around the Z-axis.
- Invariance under translation by $(0, n \cdot 2\pi\sqrt{3}, 0)$.

In other words, by rotating the *Diamond* TPMS, we obtain a hexagonal lattice (see Figure 1). The *Diamond* TPMS is also referred to as *Schwarz-D*, but more relevantly in this context as *Schwarz-H*, which has many other interesting properties [9, 10].

3. NEUTRON PHYSICS ANALYSIS WITH OPENMC

Both lattices shown in Figure 1 are evaluated with OpenMC operating in eigenvalue mode. In each lattice half of the volume is occupied by UO_2 fuel and the remaining half by water. Cladding is not included in the model; the material compositions are listed in Table I. Note that the choice of fuel and coolant is not crucial for demonstrating that both lattices exhibit similar neutron performance. Reflective boundary conditions are imposed in all three Cartesian directions for both geometries. For the *Diamond* lattice the effective multiplication factor is $k_{\text{eff}} = 1.26711 \pm 0.00013$ whereas for the *Schwarz-H* lattice we obtain $k_{\text{eff}} = 1.26715 \pm 0.00014$. These values are essentially identical, as expected, because

(a) *Diamond* — Top view (b) *Diamond* — Iso view (c) *Schwarz-H* — Top view (d) *Schwarz-H* — Iso view

Figure 1. Unit cells for rotated (*Schwarz-H*) and unrotated *Diamond* TPMS. The red volume represents the fuel, while the surrounding space represents the coolant. Cladding is not represented.

the two lattices are geometrically indistinguishable in an infinite (unbounded) geometry. A small deviation might become observable in a compact core where the neutron mean free path is comparable to the core dimensions. In such a case the intrinsic anisotropy of the lattice can lead to slightly different neutron leakage rates depending on the overall shape of the core.

Table I. Material compositions used in the OpenMC simulations.

Fuel		Water	
density [g/cm^3]	10.045	density [g/cm^3]	0.770
U234 [%]	0.009	H1 [%]	66.667
U235 [%]	1.025	O16 [%]	33.333
U236 [%]	0.005		
U238 [%]	32.285		
C12 [%]	0.014		
N14 [%]	0.015		
O16 [%]	66.647		

4. MECHANICAL ANALYSIS WITH MOOSE

The purpose of this mechanical analysis is to compare the response of the two lattice orientations under a prescribed displacement. A comprehensive mechanical analysis, including fuel performance, is beyond the scope of this paper. Simulations were performed with the MOOSE framework [11, 12]. For each lattice the bottom face was fixed (zero displacement) while the top face was displaced downwards by 1 mm. An exaggerated view of the resulting displacement field is shown in Figure 2. Both lattices share the same geometric parameters: a pitch of 5 cm, a Young's modulus of 1 GPa, and a Poisson's ratio of 0.30.

The reaction force acting on the displaced top face is calculated. To enable a fair comparison, the force is normalised by dividing it by the lattice cross-section area and multiplying by the lattice length, i.e. a force per unit length. The results are displayed on Figure 3. The normalised reaction forces are plotted in Figure 3. The *Diamond* lattice exhibits a slightly larger reaction force than the *Schwarz-H* lattice, indicating a greater resistance to the imposed displacement.

Figure 4 displays the Von Mises stress distribution for the two configurations. In the *Schwarz-H* lattice the highest stresses occur near the outer edges where wall thickness is reduced. This issue can be mitigated by choosing a slicing method that avoids thin walls. The stress field in the central region

Figure 2. Exaggerated displacement field for the two lattice orientations.

Figure 3. Normalised reaction force for each lattice orientation. The mesh refinement is expressed as the number of cell edges per centimeter.

is relatively uniform. Conversely, the *Diamond* lattice shows a more fundamental weakness: stress concentrates along the symmetry planes. These results show that the orientation of the lattice influences its response to mechanical stress.

5. FLOW ANALYSIS WITH STAR-CCM+

A preliminary CFD analysis was conducted on the Diamond and Schwarz-H lattices to compare their thermal and hydraulic performance under identical boundary conditions. In this investigation, hexagonal prisms were selected for the initial study, with the Diamond and Schwarz-H lattices having equal densities of 60%. Wall boundary conditions were imposed on the lateral sides of the hexagonal prism, with strictly axial mass flow inlet and pressure outlet flows. The working fluid used in the simulations was supercritical CO₂, with thermophysical properties consistent with those reported in [13]. Note that the choice of coolant is not critical for demonstrating the differing thermal transfer behavior of the two lattices. The physics selection and mesh settings were adopted based on the information presented in [14].

The pressure drop per unit length ($\Delta P/L$) and Nusselt number (Nu) as functions of mass flow rate are

Figure 4. Von Mises stress distribution for the two lattice orientations.

presented in Figure 5. The standard Diamond lattice (0°) exhibited a lower computed $\Delta P/L$ compared to the tilted Schwarz-H lattice (45°), while the Schwarz-H lattice demonstrates superior heat transfer performance. However, these initial results do not yet allow for definitive conclusions on the performance of each lattice.

Indeed, using a wall boundary condition on a single unit cell is not ideal, as it can block flow paths perpendicular to the z -axis and lead to an unrealistic increase in pressure drop. However, applying a periodic boundary condition is also problematic, as it allows flow velocity components perpendicular to the z -axis to be non-zero. Consequently, the computed pressure drop is also unrealistic, since coolant flow is constrained to move along the z -axis. A more representative approach would involve applying a wall boundary condition to multiple unit cells generated in all directions. However, this method is computationally expensive to mesh and would require significant refinements to our workflow before it could be implemented.

Additionally, this preliminary CFD study only evaluated a specific density, lattice size, and specific boundary conditions, which may not be representative of other potential configurations. Nonetheless, the observed differences between the two lattice configurations underscore the significance of lattice orientation on thermal behavior when developing TPMS-based fuel structures. Future work should, therefore, focus on evaluating the advantages and drawbacks of various lattice orientations under different configurations and operating conditions.

6. CONCLUSION

This paper hypothesized that a rotated version of the Schwarz-D lattice, specifically the Schwarz-H lattice, exhibits improved mechanical and cooling properties without affecting its neutron physics behavior. A mathematical analysis of the lattice was conducted to support this hypothesis. The response of each lattice to compression along the z -axis was analyzed using MOOSE. The analysis revealed that stresses were concentrated on the symmetry planes of the Schwarz-D lattice, indicating a different stress distribution compared to the Schwarz-H lattice. Neutron physics calculations using OpenMC indicated that the neutron physics properties are independent of the lattice orientation in infinite lattices. CFD analysis using STAR-CCM+ showed varying thermal behaviors depending on the lattice orientation. Despite these observed differences, definitive conclusions could not be drawn due to the lack of validation data and uncertainty quantification. Therefore, while it was not possible to fully validate the

Figure 5. Comparison between Diamond and Schwarz-H lattices.

hypothesis, the differences in mechanical and thermal behavior due to lattice orientation justify further research. Future research should focus on enhancing multidisciplinary studies to provide more definitive insights into the suitability of Diamond and Schwarz-H TPMS structures for fuel design. Mechanical analyses should incorporate fuel performance considerations, while CFD studies would benefit from comparisons with more realistic boundary conditions. Additionally, the impact of neutron streaming in fast reactor systems should be examined.

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